

**Inherited Tragedy: An Analysis of Inherited Genetic Traits and Epigenetic Trauma in the
Kennedy Family.**

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Abstract

This project presents an analysis of the genetic profile of the Kennedy family from a combined perspective between inherited genetics and epigenetics, integrating concepts of phenotypic traits, autoimmune pathologies and genetic modifications induced by chronic stress and generational trauma. From the study of specific cases, such as that of President John F. Kennedy and his nephew Robert F. Kennedy Jr., two key conditions within the family history are examined: Addison's disease and subsequent reinterpretation of this to class 2 poly glandular autoimmune syndrome (known as ASP-2) and spasmodic dysphonia, One allows for an old interpretation of the Kennedys' genetics while the other allows for a reinterpretation from advances in modern biology.

It also addresses the various psychiatric disorders that have been identified in the Kennedy gene to date, such as major depression, substance use disorders and developmental disabilities, which are traced through the family tree. The popularly called "Kennedy curse" is analyzed here from a medical perspective considering that family misfortunes may have a biological root that can be understood with the help of epigenetics.

This report has been submitted as a synthesis project for the Applied Biology class at the rural site of the LCF in the first semester (second bimester) of the 2025 academic year.

Resumen

Este proyecto presenta un análisis del perfil genético de la familia Kennedy desde una perspectiva combinada entre la genética heredada y la epigenética, integrando conceptos de rasgos fenotípicos, patologías autoinmunes y modificaciones genéticas inducidas por el estrés crónico y el trauma generacional. A partir del estudio de casos específicos, como el del presidente John F. Kennedy y su sobrino Robert F. Kennedy Jr., se examinan dos condiciones clave dentro de la historia de la familia: la enfermedad de Addison y la posterior reinterpretación de esta al síndrome autoinmune poli glandular clase 2 (conocido por sus siglas en inglés como ASP-2) y la disfonía espasmódica. Una permite una interpretación vieja sobre la genética de los Kennedy mientras que la otra a la reinterpretación desde los avances de la biología moderna.

Asimismo, se abordan los distintos trastornos psiquiátricos que se han podido evidenciar hasta la fecha en la gen Kennedy, como la depresión mayor, los trastornos por uso de sustancias y las discapacidades del desarrollo, rastreados a lo largo del árbol genealógico. La popularmente llamada "maldición Kennedy" se analiza aquí desde una perspectiva medica considerando que las desventuras familiares pueden tener una raíz biológica que se pueda entender con ayuda de la epigenética.

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Este informe fue presentado como proyecto de síntesis para la clase de Biología Aplicada en la sede rural del Liceo Campestre Facatativá durante el primer semestre (segundo bimestre) del año académico 2025.

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To be born a Kennedy is to inherit more than a name. It is to carry a legacy of power, illness, and trauma.

As documented by Wilson (1947) the Kennedy clan is an ancient family on American soil, having settled with Dr. John Kennedy, a man of Irish origin who was kidnapped and sold into slavery and later freed. He had as descendants a son named Thomas Kennedy, which later would become the primary ancestor of the Kennedys.

There are several genetic traits evident in the bloodline of Thomas Kennedy that appear to be genotypically dominant in nature, favoring the expression of certain phenotypes, these include:

A prominent jaw and elongated facial complexion, tall stature, usually exceeding 1.80 m. or 5'11 ft. due probably to a polygenic trait, and a clear and powerful voice, but prone to vocal problems.

The genetic profile of the Kennedy's not only ends in aesthetics, but also involves serious medical problems.

According to Macchia et al. (2020) in an article studying one of its most prominent members and his medical history: President John Fitzgerald Kennedy served as a sample to create much of what is publicly known about the genetic diseases that run in the family, including Addison's disease, a form of adrenal insufficiency, hypothyroidism and celiac disease, although the article reveals that the president's pathological picture may be more different than one might think,

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suffering from an autoimmune disease called autoimmune polyglandular syndrome type 2, abbreviated as APS-2.

The pathological picture of the president would not only indicate a serious genetic disorder, but also opens the door to analyze the possibility that the Kennedys had other particularities in their genes.

Being one of the leaders of the free world may have entailed epigenetic factors, including chronic stress, exposure to trauma at a young age, which may have had a significant impact according to the study by Thumfart et al. (2021), and other responsibilities of the office may not only have led to a greater manifestation of the syndrome, but may have directly affected the president's quality of life.

It is because of this clinical picture that the grounds for arguing that Kennedys are carriers of serious genetic conditions are more than sufficient, which is why for this report I have chosen to analyze two of their conditions, Addison's disease and spasmodic dysphonia.

Addison's disease, formally known as primary adrenal failure with an autoimmune-based etiology, in this endocrine system disorder causes the immune system to actively destroy the adrenal cortex, creating deficiencies in hormones such as aldosterone, DHEA or dehydroepiandrosterone and cortisol. This leads to a chronic hormone deficiency class, affecting the stress response, the osmotic balance of the body and in general, the cardiovascular and metabolic function, and can lead to direct effects on the quality of life and even psychotic attacks. (Røyrvik & Husebye, 2022; Sanat & Mohajeri-Tehrani, 2022).

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Spasmodic dysphonia is a rare neurological speech disorder that presents in the form of focal dystonia, i.e. the brain has problems in the fine motor execution of speech, so it does not affect the left frontal lobe and left temporal lobe, i.e. the Broca and Wernicke areas respectively. The patient is in perfect condition to execute speech, but has problems in doing so. The disorder affects the descending motor circuits, that is, the nucleus ambiguus, responsible for controlling the musculature of the larynx, basal ganglia and the supplementary motor cortex along the primary motor area. One Kennedy exponent who has stated to suffer from this disease in public interviews is Robert F. Kennedy Jr., current secretary of the department of health and human services of the United States (LaMotte, 2025; Kandel, Schwartz, Jessell, Siegelbaum, & Hudspeth, 2013; Aminoff, Dedo, & Izdebski, 1978).

The Kennedys, in addition to being a family that appears to be condemned to their own physiological genetic diseases, also seem to have a tendency to mental illnesses from historical reconstructions, including: intellectual development disorders with suspected disruptive behavior disorder in the case of Rosemary Kennedy, alcohol and substance use disorder in several of the men in the family, Major depressive disorders and generalized anxiety in JFK and Ted Kennedy, as well as the opioid consumption disorder of Robert F. Kennedy Jr.

Because the Kennedys are prone to different genetic diseases, it is almost certain that many of their members may have been asymptomatic patients or carriers of some of these disorders, particularly autoimmune disorders with polygenic inheritance. To be a carrier of a genetic disorder is, according to Jorde et al. (2020) to be "An individual who carries one copy of a recessive mutant allele. Carriers are usually unaffected by the condition but may pass the allele

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to their children, who can be affected if they inherit a second mutant allele from the other parent."

These patterns in the family's mental health could point to a major psychiatric vulnerability that would involve polygenic inheritance and epigenetic modulation due to trauma, stress and high socio-political pressure as public figures as revealed in the memoir of Patrick Kennedy (Heil, 2021; American Psychiatric Association, 2022)

This is when epigenetics comes to play a key role in how the specific context of the Kennedys is analyzed, understanding that there may be changes in genetic expression that do not come from the DNA itself but instead come from chemical modifications and their associated proteins, it is when we can clearly see the importance of understanding this kind of change, that it becomes crucial to determine the role of environmental and lifestyle factors as well as in phenotype inheritance, that is, understanding that epigenetic factors may have an important role not only in diagnosis, but also in the treatment and correction of these in case of unfavorable conditions. (Farsetti et al., 2023)

The fruit of these epigenetic consequences for this family could be attributed to the popularly known "Kennedy Curse," which refers to all the traumatic events the family has been through, and a study by Jawaid et al. (2018) suggests that human genetics can respond to stress by

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methylation, histone modification, and noncoding RNA and that these reactions are often heritable across generations. (ABC News, 2012)

So, to finish synthesizing all that has been exposed at this point, the Kennedy clan seems to have a genetic history of mental illness, addiction, genetic disorders possibly caused by epigenetic conditions that eventually affected both the family's moral and physical health. It can be said that the Kennedy gene not only has even today a great influence on American politics, but that thanks to this public life, tragic events for entire generations of the family, the final inference would be established that the Kennedy legacy is not only of great political moments and tragedies, it is something that would be written in their genes.

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Appendix A: Kennedy Simplified Family Tree (Not to Scale)

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